

Political Socialization in New Democracies Legacies of Repression and Pre-Democratic Partisanship

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Study Motivation (Abstract)

In the broader project, we develop a framework for understanding political attitudes, behaviors, and identities in new democracies after transition from authoritarian rule. In doing so, we combine findings from an established literature on the role of political socialization through education systems and repression to understand how experiences under authoritarianism crystalize the political attitudes, behaviors, and identities that matter after transition.

In this paper, we focus on understanding the influence of experiences of repression, both at the individual and family level, on political attitudes, behaviors, and identities. Work on repression in autocracies finds that experiences of repression are integral to the formation and transmission of partisan preferences and political identities long after the termination of repression. We seek to build on this research in three ways in order to understand the long-lasting legacies of repression on political attitudes, behaviors, and identities, as well as the mechanisms through which these changes obtain.

First, we conceptualize repression as a treatment of degree and measure variation in exposure to repression. We operationalize repression in this study as arrests and measure the degree to which individuals are exposed by: (1) whether they themselves are arrested or (2) whether members of their family, friends, or local community are arrested. We believe this captures important variation in the degree to which individuals, families, and communities are exposed to repression.

Second, we design our study with the individual, rather than the group or community, as the unit of analysis. Recent studies on the legacies of repression often explore effects at the community level, and in doing so assume that all community members are uniformly affected by repression and their political attitudes, behaviors, and identities are changed in the same way and direction. However, the historical empirical record demonstrates that individuals, families, and networks are often differently affected by repression, even within a highly repressive environment.

Third, we seek to understand how individual experiences of repression under authoritarian regimes not only condition partisan preferences and identities after transition but also political participation – both whether individuals participate in politics and who they vote for when they do.

This pre-analysis plan outlines how we intend to examine the relationship between individual-level experiences of state repression and political attitudes, behaviors, and identities in Tunisia, an important and rare contemporary case of successful (and still ongoing) democratic transition. This paper combines a nationally-representative, face-to-face survey conducted in 2017 with a phone survey of sibling pairs in 2021 to examine how direct and proximate experiences with repression under authoritarian regimes affect political identities, preferences, and behaviors after democratization, with a focus on how family and community socialization transmits these effects even after the autocratic regime has been overthrown.

Pre-Registration (using aspredictor.org template)

1. Data Collection Have any data been collected for this study already?

We use data from a 2017 study to motivate a new phone survey of sibling pairs to be conducted in May 2021 (public health conditions permitting). No data for the new survey has been collected.

2. Hypothesis What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

Work on repression in authoritarian regimes finds that experiences of repression are integral to the formation and transmission of partisan preferences (Balcells 2012; Rozenas et al., 2017; Lupu and Peisakhin, 2017; Blaydes, 2018; Rozenas and Zhukov, 2019; Nugent 2020) after the termination of repression. In these studies, exposure to repression tends to correlate with stronger political attitudes and identities that favor the in-group, through the process of group identity formation.

Moreover, existing research that looks at the more proximate effects of arrests indicates that repression can have a differential impact on participation among those who were arrested and those in the arrestee's social circle. The evidence on repression and future political mobilization is more mixed. Sullivan and Davenport (2017) find that activists who personally experienced state repression subsequently challenge the government more than those who did not experience direct repression. However, research on the direct effect of arrest in the U.S. suggests that even short stints in prison can decrease the likelihood of voting in the next election (Weaver and Lerman, 2010).

The evidence on the effects of repression on the family and friends of incarcerated individuals is also mixed. In the U.S. context, Walker (2014) finds that individuals who have proximate rather than direct contact with the carceral state are more likely to vote and participate in politics. White (2019), however, finds that household members of an individual convicted or incarcerated experience a small decrease in their likelihood of voting, but the effect is short-lived. These results suggest that the effect of arrests among those directly and proximately affected may be heterogenous.

This research also identifies several potential mechanisms through which repression, or specifically arrest, can have an effect on political attitudes, identities, and behaviors. The indirect impact of arrest on family and friends can operate through family socialization. Family members may share information about a repressive experience or develop their own sense of "linked fate" within their family or community (Balcells 2012; Lawrence, 2017; Lupu and Peisakhin, 2017; Blaydes, 2018; Nugent 2020). Moreover, an arrestee who was released during the Ben Ali era continued to feel the effects of the arrest socially and economically. Based on her research on the economic effects of repression, Hibou (2011) writes that, after prison, former arrestees experienced a form of "social death" (p. 6).

Evidence from the 2017 nationally representative survey suggests that exposure to repression matters for subsequent political attitudes, behaviors, and identities in Tunisia, the case analyzed in our study. Tunisian citizens whose family and community members who were arrested were more likely to vote in subsequent democratic elections and to vote against the old regime (i.e. those responsible for past repression). While individuals who were arrested under the previous authoritarian regime were less likely to turn out to vote in democratic elections, in line with research on the demobilizing effects of repression, those who did vote were strong partisans and were more likely to vote for the former opposition and anti-regime parties.

Building on existing literature and our preliminary findings, we consider several possible effects of repression (measured as arrest) under authoritarianism on political attitudes, behaviors, and identities after a transition to democracy. We set out three groups of hypotheses; in each group, the first focuses on individual exposure while the second focuses on community-level exposure.

Attitudes:

1. Direct repression *increases* opposition to political actors and policies associated with the perpetrators.
 - a. Manifested in more support for democracy, less support for old-regime, more support for lustration
2. The family and friends of a repressed individual are *more likely* to oppose political actors associated with the perpetrators.
 - a. Manifested in more support for democracy, less support for old-regime, more support for lustration
 - b. More people they know who were repressed, larger effect

Behaviors:

3. Direct repression *decreases* political participation. When the directly repressed vote, they are more likely to vote for the former opposition.
 - a. Less likely to vote, less likely to be registered
 - b. When they do vote, more likely to vote for Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from the authoritarian period.
 - c. The harsher/more extensive the repression, larger effect (less likely to vote, but more likely to support opposition if they do)
4. Alternatively, direct repression *increases* political participation, and the directly repressed are more likely to vote for the opposition.
 - a. More likely to vote, more likely to be registered
 - b. More likely to vote for Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from the authoritarian period.
 - c. The harsher/more extensive the repression, larger effect (more likely to vote and more likely to support opposition if they do)
5. The family and friends of a repressed individual are *more likely* to participate in politics.
 - a. More likely to vote, more likely to be registered
 - b. More likely to vote for Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from the authoritarian period.
 - c. More people they know who were repressed, larger effect

Identities:

1. Direct repression *increases* identification with oppositional actors.
 - a. More likely to identify with Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from the authoritarian period
 - b. Among those who identify with Ennahda, stronger identification with Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from authoritarian period than partisans who were not repressed

2. The family and friends of a repressed individual are *more likely* to identify with oppositional actors.
 - a. More likely to identify with Ennahda or non-Islamist opposition from the authoritarian period.
 - b. More people they know who were repressed, larger effect

With regards to the mechanism through which repression influences political attitudes, behaviors, and identities, we hypothesize that personal relationships and familial political socialization are both significant factors. We expect that any correlation between exposure to repression through others and political attitudes, behaviors, and identities will be stronger the closer the personal relationship is (i.e., we expect that the correlation to be stronger for family members than for neighbors or community members) and will monotonically increase with the number of arrested individuals known. In addition, we expect that those who have been repressed or those who know others who have been repressed are more likely to have spoken about this experience and/or politics with other trust community members, such as family and friends.

3. **Dependent Variables** Describe the key dependent variables(s) specifying how they will be measured

Voter Registration:

1. Are you registered to vote?

Political Participation:

2. Did you vote in the 2019 parliamentary election?
3. Did you vote in the 2019 presidential election (round 1)?
4. Did you vote in the 2019 presidential election (round 2)?
5. In the last year have you:
 - a. Attended a municipal council meeting?
 - b. Participated in a demonstration, rally, or sit-in?
 - c. Engaged in a political discussion on social media?
 - d. Contacted your MP?
 - e. Participated in a political campaign?

Political Orientation:

6. Before 2011, were you a member of any of the following parties or political movements?
7. In the 2019 parliamentary elections, which list did you vote for?
8. In the 2019 presidential elections (round 1), which candidate did you vote for?
9. In the 2019 presidential elections (round 2), which candidate did you vote for?
10. Do you usually think of yourself as close to any particular political party? If so, which one?

4. **Conditions** How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

There is no random assignment for this study. We will select a random sample of the nationally-representative survey sample and conduct a survey with their siblings.

5. **Analyses** Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question.

Our primary independent variables are respondents' self-reported experiences with state repression before 2011. We will include questions on the respondents' personal experience with arrest as well as

other forms of state repression (imprisonment, house arrest, exile, economic sanctions). We will also ask respondents about whether their immediate family, extended family, friends, or broader community members (neighbors and co-workers) experienced repression prior to 2011.

Additionally, we will collect data on potential mechanisms of transmission, including frequency of discussions about politics or experiences with repression with family, friends, and community members and feelings of victimhood.

6. Outliers and Exclusions Describe exactly how outliers will be defined and handled, and your precise rule(s) for excluding observations

N/A

7. Sample Size How many observations will be collected or what will determine sample size?

We plan to conduct a nationally representative survey of 1500 Tunisian adults (18+) with a secondary survey of 750 siblings of primary survey respondents.

8. Other Anything else you would like to preregister? (e.g. secondary analyses, variables collected for explanatory purposes, unusual analyses planned?)

N/A